

European Posting of Workers: An Exploratory Analysis of Requirements of the European Union Directive and Perceptions about the Respect of Working Conditions

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Abstract: This exploratory study analyses the requirements of the Directive on European Posting of Workers and the perceptions about the respect of working conditions in Spain and Poland. A posted worker is an employee who is sent by his employer, for a given period, to carry out his tasks in the territory of a Member State other than the State in which he normally works. Working conditions is one of the thorniest issues that have led to different revisions of the European Union (EU) Directives on posting of workers. The promulgation of posting of Workers Directive (EU PWD 96/71/EC) and its Enforcement Directive (PWD 2014/67/EU) contributed to specify the working conditions of employees sent by their employers to work to another EU country. To achieve the objective of this study, a survey to different social agents was conducted (public officers, trade unions members, posted workers, and employers). The sample consisted of 251 participants from Poland (65%) and Spain (35%). The findings show that, according to the participants, the working conditions are respected partially: minimum wage levels, times of rest and vacation periods, and conditions of work are some of the aspects that are not respected in hosting countries. The main key improvement of working conditions that brings the recent revised Directive (PWD 2018/957) are discussed. Some implications and future perspectives are underlined.

Keywords: working conditions, posting workers directive, protection of workers, equal pay and opportunities.

Destacamento Europeu de Trabalhadores: Uma Análise Exploratória dos Requisitos da Diretiva da União Europeia e Perceções sobre o Respeito das Condições de Trabalho

Resumo: Este estudo exploratório analisa os requisitos da Diretiva sobre o Destacamento Europeu de Trabalhadores e as percepções sobre o respeito pelas condições de trabalho em Espanha e na Polónia. Um trabalhador destacado é um trabalhador que é enviado pelo seu empregador, por um determinado período, para executar as suas tarefas no território de um Estado-Membro diferente daquele em que normalmente trabalha. As condições de trabalho são uma das questões mais espinhosas que levaram a diferentes revisões das diretivas da União Europeia (UE) sobre o destacamento de trabalhadores. A promulgação da Diretiva de Destacamento de Trabalhadores (EU PWD 96/71/EC) e da sua Diretiva de Execução (PWD 2014/67/UE) contribuiu para especificar as condições de trabalho dos trabalhadores enviados pelos seus empregadores para trabalhar noutro país da UE. Para atingir o objetivo deste estudo, foi realizado um inquérito a diferentes agentes sociais (funcionários públicos, sindicalistas, trabalhadores destacados e empregadores). A amostra consistiu em 251 participantes da Polónia (65%) e Espanha (35%). As conclusões mostram que, segundo os participantes, as condições de trabalho são parcialmente respeitadas: os níveis de salário mínimo, os períodos de descanso e férias e as condições de trabalho são alguns dos aspetos que não são respeitados nos países de acolhimento. São discutidas as principais melhorias nas condições de trabalho trazidas pela recente Diretiva revista (PWD 2018/957). Algumas implicações e perspetivas futuras são sublinhadas.

Palavras-chave: condições de trabalho, diretiva sobre destacamento de trabalhadores, proteção dos trabalhadores, igualdade salarial e de oportunidades.

1. Introduction

The working conditions remain an issue that is still generating challenges and debates in the European Union (EU) particularly when a worker leaves his ordinary position to go to work in another Member country. One of the fundamental social and economic freedoms of the EU is the mobility of the workforce (the free movement of persons, goods, services, and capital). In that framework of free movement of people, one company can temporarily send its employees to another Member State to provide services; this is what is known as "posting of workers" within the EU internal single markets. Accordingly, a posted worker is an employee who is sent by his employer, for a limited period, to carry out his work in the territory of a Member State other than the State in which he normally works. The posting of workers in the EU remains regulated by the national labour law of the Member State in accordance with EU regulation [Posting Workers Directives (PWD) 96/71/EC; PWD 2014/67/EU, and PWD 2018/957]. The implementation of the PWD 96/71/EC has played a crucial role particularly in the social cohesion and protection of posted workers' rights. It defines the working conditions that should be respected when an employee is sent to another country in the EU internal single market. Moreover, the Directive ensures the legal platform of work and cooperation between EU Member States. The PWD 96/71/EC, its enforcement EU-PWD 2014/67 and the revised PWD 2018/957, aim not only to promote the cross-border provisions of services, but also to protect the posted workers' rights and obligations. Besides, the Services Directive (2006/123/EC) and the Social Security Regulation (883/2004) allow the posted employees who are hired in the EU internal labour market to work in another Member State, with the working conditions of the sending country, unless the existence of specific regulation in the hosting country. According to the 2020 annual report on labour mobility published by the European Commission, there were approximately 13.2 million of EU citizens who lived and worked in another EU country than their own, representing 3.4% of the total employment in the EU. The main EU countries of destination are Germany, Spain, Italy and France. The main countries senders of EU movers for working are Romania, Poland, Portugal, Croatia, and Bulgaria (EU labour mobility report, 2020; Fries-Tersch at al., 2022).

The Enforcement Directive (PWD 2014/67/EU) and the revised posting of Workers Directive (PWD 2018/957) are complementary to each other and reinforce the EU regulation. Posting of workers is a big concern since the rights and obligations of both, employees and employers could be involved particularly in terms of social protection and working conditions which include the work periods, rest periods, paid annual holidays, rates of pay, conditions of hiring-out of workers, health, safety and hygiene at work, conditions of employment of pregnant women, equality of treatment between men and women and other provisions on non-discrimination. The EU Members States are not yet capable of fully providing the cross-border provision of services through equal rules on monetary and non-monetary remuneration applicable to both posted and to local workers. In 2014, the Enforcement Directive (PWD 2014/67/EU) was adopted to improve the Directive (PWD 96/71/EC). It is an additional regulation that specifies a common framework of appropriate provisions, measures, and control mechanisms for better posting of workers and more uniform implementation, application, and enforcement in implementation of Directive (EU PWD 96/71/EC). The interpretation of working conditions remained a dominant subject of debates which led to unfair practices such as social

dumping, unequal treatment between local and posted workers. (Riesco-Sanz, García & Maira, 2019; Uğur, 2020).

There are different debates on the need for greater social cohesion within Europe as well as greater integration to solve the problem of social dumping and to improve working conditions for the social well-being of European citizens. Initiatives such as “the Mobility Package Directive on Posted workers” or “the European Pillar of Social Rights” are targeting to propose solutions to the current social dimensions of the EU. The increased cross border mobility of companies and workers’ demands require urgent actions to be taken as they are threatening social cohesion and the support for the European Union as a common project. The broad involvement of candidate countries from Eastern Europe (Albania, Montenegro, North Macedonia, and Serbia) and United Kingdom (UK) Brexit situation motivate the implementation of discussions and joint initiatives with social partners from other EU countries to achieve a better protection of posted workers’ rights and to generate free and fair movement of workers, and higher employment levels.

Due to its nature and structure, posting of workers continues to have different attitudes among EU citizens. Social dumping is associated with problems related to no-respect of workers’ rights, unfair competition, and deterioration of workers’ employment conditions. The harmonisation of social standards and working conditions are the pillars that sustain the social cohesion and the competitiveness of the economies of the EU Member States. Therefore, the main objective of this exploratory study is to analyse the attitudes and opinions of main social actors of labour involved in cross-border in Poland and Spain (public officers, trade unions members, posted workers, and employers) on working conditions of posting workers, in the framework of the EU Directive of posting of workers. Moreover, it also analyses the irregularities and difficulties in monitoring and the provisions of the posting of workers. Poland is one of the main sending Member States in absolute terms, followed by other countries such as France, UK, Germany, and Spain. In Poland and in Spain, the Directives have been transposed in their respective national laws in the framework of the transnational provision of services.

2. Working Conditions: conceptual framework

The term "working conditions" encompasses many variables related to work activity, which can affect both the performance and well-being of workers; and they have been studied from various disciplines and scientific fields (ILO, 2015; Nappo, 2019; Kaltenecker, 2022). Salary, hours, work organisation, health and safety at work, vacations, possibility of promotion, reconciliation between personal and work life are some of the elements that identify working conditions. They englobe working environment and all existing circumstances affecting labour in the workplace (WHO, 2006; ILO, 2015). From the perspective of International Labour Office (ILO), occupational safety and health (OSH) is defined as the science of the anticipation, recognition, evaluation and control of the hazards arising in or from the workplace that could damage the health and well-being of workers, taking in account the possible impact on the environment and communities (Alli, 2008). Working conditions are an extremely important issue for both workers and companies and for society. They include any specific aspect in which the work activity occurs such as factors of the physical environment in which it is carried out and the temporary circumstances in which it occurs, the circumstances under which workers perform their work, the attributes, or characteristics of the tasks to be performed.

In fact, in the Preamble of its constitution, the ILO states the following about working conditions:

“...And whereas conditions of labour exist involving such injustice, hardship and privation to large numbers of people as to produce unrest so great that the peace and harmony of the world are imperilled; and an improvement of those conditions is urgently required; as, for example, by the regulation of the hours of work, including the establishment of a maximum working day and week, the regulation of the labour supply, the prevention of unemployment, the provision of an adequate living wage, the protection of the worker against sickness, disease and injury arising out of his employment, ...” (ILO, 1919, p.5).

Digital transformation, competitiveness among companies, globalisation of products and services, and requirements of the labour market are current contexts that are changing the working conditions in terms of working hours, safety at workplace, etc.. Thus, shift work has become a trend to almost all occupational sectors with significant economic and social repercussions for the company, the individual and the community (Alli, 2008; Arcangeli et al., 2019; Lindholma et al., 2020). Good working conditions contribute to the well-being of workers and the success of organisations. Posture-related risks include exposure to vibrations, tiring positions, lifting people, carrying heavy loads and repetitive movements are risk factors that can cause serious diseases and working accidents (Thébaud-Mony et al., 2015; Smits et al., 2017; Schneid, 2019; Mullen et al., 2024).

Working conditions are indicators of social peace, equity, health, and well-being in general. When they are not adequate, they must be improved as they cover a wide range of topics and issues, from remuneration, working hours (time worked, rest periods and working hours) to the reconciliation of work and personal or family life, such as also the physical conditions and mental demands imposed in the workplace. All these aspects make it difficult to reach consensus on a clear, single, and acceptable definition for all. It is easier to describe the characteristics of working conditions than to offer a universally acceptable definition. Research trends (Gerber et al., 1988; Wooden et al., 2016; Saka et al., 2023; Myungsun et al., 2023) underline that working conditions is a multidimensional construct; and there is a great number of aspects related to working conditions that can be summarised as follows:

(1) Environmental conditions that refer to the physical work environment. These are the variables that are most considered as physical conditions in the strictest sense (Hanna &, Salah, 2017; Ochoa & Coello-Montecel, 2021). Environmental conditions comprise at least three types of differentiated variables: (a) the physical environment mainly refers to magnitudes such as temperature, humidity, noise level, lighting, ventilation and air purity (harmful substances, pollutants, and dust), existence of vibrations, and even the general conditions of cleanliness, hygiene and order in the workplace; (b) the space and geographical variables have mainly to do with the existence of sufficient space to be able to carry out the tasks related to the work, the distribution of that space, its configuration and the relationships established between the space and the workers (privacy/intimacy, territoriality, density/overcrowding, isolation conditions); (c) the ergonomic and architectural design aspects of the workplace, referring to both the space and the materials and equipment needed to perform the job. Specifically, it involves the configuration, distribution, and ergonomic design of the workplace to avoid posture-related risks.

(2) Employment conditions are hiring conditions such as salary conditions, stability and security of employment and other aspects related to the situation of the labour market which include unemployment rates of the sector or region, social security benefits, legislative framework for hiring. (Campos-Serna et al., 2013; Ochoa & Coello-Montecel, 2021; Myungsun et al., 2023). Other elements that are often included in this category are the existence or not of collective agreements, membership rates in union organisations, the evolution of the industrial sector in which the organisation is located, other benefits (salary or not), or the regulation on vacations.

(3) The safety and health conditions are the conditions under which the work is carried out, in relation to the prevention of occupational hazards and the risks of accidents, as well as the appearance of occupational diseases or pathologies (McConnell, 2003; Kalwij & Vermeulen, 2008; Wooden et al., 2016; Saka et al., 2023). There is a vast field of studies, such as hygiene and safety at work and occupational health, where all those aspects of work can cause physical, chemical, or mechanical risks. Measures aimed at risk protection, prevention measures and safety conditions are also included.

(4) Work organisation and processes refer to the organisation and division of work, the demands of the specific position and other aspects related to its performance (Gerber et al., 1988; Ochoa & Coello-Montecel, 2021; Dütsch, 2022). The temporal aspects and sequencing of the work (length of the working day, workload, rhythm and cadence of the production process, variations in the workflow, pressures and deadlines for completion), the level of process demands (quality standards, peaks in production), the degree of supervision and control over the work, the demands of the position and work overload (both physical, psychological and emotional), the work posture or the sequencing of movements, as well as the functional interdependence with other positions and/or sections or the flow of information, products and work processes could be included in this block.

(5) Psychosocial and/or organisational conditions are related to interaction: interpersonal relationships in the work context (communication with colleagues, social support, interpersonal conflicts, cohesion of the work team), the work environment (the emphasis in innovation, support for creativity, respect for rules and procedures), aspects related to workers' control over their environment (for instance, accessibility of resources, degree of control about the task), the degree of participation in organisational decisions, and even social expectations about one's work (Gerber et al., 1988; Ochoa & Coello-Montecel, 2021; Saka et al., 2023).

Working conditions cover the working environment and the existing circumstances that affect the work and the employees' well-being in the workplace which includes, among other aspects, remuneration, leaves, allowances, job hours, health & safety, workload, and job security (Alli, 2008; Mullen et al., 2024). The EU Strategic Framework on Health and Safety at Work (EU Strategic Framework) is an intent to ensure that the European Union (EU) continues to play a leading role in promoting high standards for working conditions both within Europe and internationally. The focus is put on companies that have to put in place effective and efficient risk prevention strategies (European Commission, 2021).

3. Working conditions and posting workers Directives in the European Union

According to the Annual Report on Intra-EU Labour Mobility 2022 (2023), there were approximately 12.9 million of EU citizens who lived and worked in another EU country than their own, representing 3.4% of the total employment in the EU (Fries-Tersch et al., 2022). In 2021, despite the negative impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on intra-EU posting was

still visible, the total number of issued PDs A1 in the EU-27 and EFTA amounted to 3.6 million (-4.4% compared to 2020 and -22.4% compared to 2019). In 2019, the most Member States that sent cross-border workers were France (374,000 or 20%), Germany (241,000 or 11%) and Poland (206,000 or 11%). Between 2017 and 2018, the countries that increased the number of cross-border workers were mainly Bulgaria (+66%), the UK (+52%), Slovenia (+31%), Spain (+21%), Luxembourg (+21%) and Croatia (+12%). Altogether they received 50% of the total postings in Europe and their number of EU-28 movers was growing faster than EU average compared to 2015. Germany and the UK are the principal destination countries for EU movers, with inflows of 318,000 and 194,000 people respectively in 2017. In 2018, Romania, Poland, Italy, Portugal and Bulgaria remained the main sending countries, each having between 100,000 and 160,000 nationals leaving the country for another EU country. The nature of posting of workers' context is a very complex issue in terms of actors involved, policy implemented in the EU (and in each specific EU Member State), obstacles to overcome and gaps of some undefined aspects of the Directive.

The Directive (PWD 1996/71) provides the legal framework that protects the rights and establishes a list of working conditions that must be granted to avoid violation of workers' rights. In each EU Member State, the minimum standards ("hard core") of conditions for posted workers that must be included: (a) maximum work periods and minimum rest periods; (b) minimum paid annual holidays; (c) the minimum rates of pay, including overtime rates; (d) the conditions of hiring-out of workers; (e) health, safety and hygiene at work; (f) protective measures with regard to the terms and conditions of employment of pregnant women or women who have recently given birth, of children and of young people and (g) equality of treatment between men and women and other provisions on non-discrimination. It is important to underline that the standards applicable to posted workers must reflect at least the minimum conditions of local workers in the Member State where the worker is posted. However, it does not ban employers from going beyond those standards, considering applying more favourable working conditions to posted workers.

In 2014, the PWD 2014/67 (the Enforcement of the PWD 96/71/EC) was introduced in response to improper application of PWD 96/71/EC and limitations detected in the protection of posted workers. Its aim is to ensure an appropriate level of protection of the rights of posted workers for the cross-border provision of services, in particular the enforcement of the terms and conditions of employment included in the previous Directive (PWD 96/71/EC). Besides, it should facilitate the exercise of the freedom to provide services and promote fair competition in the EU labour market. In brief, the enforcement Directive (PWD 2014/67/EU) stresses on the following objectives: (a) to increase the awareness of workers and companies about their rights and obligations as regards the terms and conditions of employment; (b) to improve cooperation between national authorities in charge of posting activities; besides, it also clarifies the definition of posting (to reduce the practices of 'letter-box' in which companies use posting of workers formula to circumvent the legislation); (c) to define responsibilities of Member States to verify compliance with the rules laid down in the PWD 96/71/EC (designation of specific enforcement authorities responsible for verifying compliance; it also ensures the supervisory and enforcement measures for service providers established in the Member State); (d) to require posting companies to designate a contact person for liaison with the enforcement authorities; to declare their identity, the number of workers to be posted and

the posting modalities; and to keep basic employment documents available; (e) to improve the enforcement of rights and the handling of complaints, by requiring both host and home Member States to insure posted workers, with the support of trade unions and other interested third parties; (f) to ensure that administrative penalties and fines imposed on service providers by one Member State for failure to respect the requirements of the Directive (PWD 96/71/EC) can be enforced and recovered in another Member State.

Among other aspects to take in consideration, the Enforcement Directive (PWD 2014/67/EU) provides some changes regarding legal clarity: it improves access to information, and cooperation between national authorities. Moreover, it provides measures to prevent and to sanction any abuse, to monitor compliance and to control measures and subcontracting liability, reinforcement of control mechanisms (inspectorate) and the cross-border enforcement of administrative penalties and fines. One of the important rules promoted by the PWD 2014/67/EU is that Member States are obliged to take the appropriate measures to ensure that the information on the terms and conditions of employment referred to in Directive 96/71 is made generally available free of charge in a clear, transparent, comprehensive, and easily accessible way at a distance and by electronic means (Article 5, 1). It also provides norms that can improve and enhance administrative cooperation between the national authorities of the Member States to facilitate the implementation, application, and enforcement in practice of PWD 2014/67/EU and PWD 96/71/EC. However, despite of the improvement in comparison with the PWD 96/71/EC, the Directive (PWD 2014/67/EU) showed important weaknesses related to lack of transparency, unfair competition, unacceptable practices in employment conditions (wage, allowances, leaves and vacations), social dumping, lack of availability of information on posting activities (Dhéret & Ghimis, 2016; Melin, 2021).

In 2018 the European Parliament revised the posting of workers' regulation particularly the Directive 96/71 and its Enforcement Directive (PWD 2014/67/EU) and promulgated the revised Directive (PWD 2018/957). This new legislation clarifies some dark aspects which were subjects of violation of posted workers' rights. It reinforces the legal bases of free movement of services, and strengthens the "social dimension" in terms of workers' protection. The recent Directive (PWD 2018/957) makes some relevant contributions that could be underlined as following: (a) it confirms the concept of posting of workers under the legal basis of free movement of services; (b) it promotes the principle of 'equal pay for equal work at the same place and conditions; (c) it introduces a maximum duration limit of twelve months to posting; (d) and it provides for equal treatment of posted temporary agency workers with agency workers recruited locally in the host Member State. This is a very critical aspect since it extends the validity of universally binding collective agreements to posted workers in all economic sectors in any EU Member State, including the EU country Candidates from Eastern Europe (Serbia, Montenegro, Albania, Macedonia).

The most important changes that the Directive (PWD 2018/957) provides is related to the remuneration of posted workers, temporary agency workers and terms of posting activities. It pretends to solve the problems related to the unclear interpretation of terms and conditions of employment. It refers clearly to "remuneration" instead of "minimum rates of pay". The recent Directive (PWD 2018/957) has stipulated that the posted workers will benefit from the same treatment in terms of remuneration and work conditions as local workers. This point allows national legislation to specify all constituent elements of remuneration in accordance with the national regulation and collective agreement (Article

3, paragraph 8). In this case, the “remuneration” includes mandatory elements stipulated by national law as well collective agreements and arbitration awards of general application. Furthermore, the revised Directive would help to avoid the unfair practices such as “envelope wages” or “cash-in-hand” whereby the employers pay officially only part of the salary, meanwhile the rest is given to employees unofficially.

By specifying the working conditions applicable to posted workers, the EU Directives aim, among other aspects, to prevent “social dumping”. It occurs when an employer tries to gain unfair advantage in the common market offering inferior employment conditions. Social dumping can be defined as the practice undertaken by self-interested market participants by undermining or evading existing social regulations with the aim of gaining competitive advantage (Bernaciak, 2014). Originally the expression of “social dumping” was used mainly by trade unions as a political key word to combat “cheap workers” from poorer member states that are working in richest EU countries. Over time even the European Commission used this term “social dumping” to express the practices of violation of posted workers’ rights. European Parliament reported three practices as social dumping (European Parliament, 2016b): (a) regulatory evasion which is the violation of regulations and concealing violations vis-à-vis regulatory authorities; (b) regulatory arbitrage which is the exploitation of benefits generated from differences between national systems; and (c) regulatory conformance which is the manipulation of regulatory rules to generate benefits. The revision of the EU Directives on Posted Workers aims to eradicate social dumping and to address these kinds of issues by adopting new regulations to promote the “same pay for the same work in the same place” principle across Member States. To sum up, social dumping is a concept related, among other aspects, to the posting of workers' issues, to mobility, to wages, and to social security. It is generally described as a set of practices on national, international, or cross-border work level that aim to gain competitive advantage by adopting unfair and abusive practices (Nuffel & Afanasjeva, 2018; Rennuy, 2020; Driguez, 2021). It is developed as a practice of self-interested markets that consists of undermining or evading the regulations to gain a competitive advantage by deteriorating the working conditions of workers.

Despite different reforms, posting of workers Directives is still not strong enough to guarantee the respect for the rights of posted workers in all European Union countries. Working conditions continue to be a recurring issue, and they are still subject of wrong interpretation which have consequences in terms of social dumping, unequal treatment between local and posted workers, unpaid overtime, unequal work conditions, and insufficient or lack of training for work safety (Głowacka, 2019; Novitz & Andrijasevic, 2020). Without profound changes, posting Directives will continue to be an instrument with limitations to encourage social cohesion and protection of workers, to fight against social exclusion and discrimination, and to promote equal treatment and the protection of human health. All of these problems related to unfair practices and violation of the workers’ rights must be addressed to achieve a “Social Europe” in which is the heart of the European project of the construction of a single European market in which people, capital, goods and Services would circulate not only freely but predominantly for the well-being of all. Among the aspects to improve, four of them should have a consideration priority: (a) to reinforce the role of the European Labour authority (ELA), (b) to implement the joint cross-border inspections, (c) to promote the availability of information on posting legislation and activities, and (d) to reinforce the involvement and participation of social actors for posting of workers’ activities.

4. Methodological approach

4.1. Procedure

This research arises from the importance of cooperation between Spain and Poland where there are several cooperation agreements. Poland and Spain have a long experience of bilateral cooperation in terms of immigration, mobility and workers' posting. This study was carried out within the framework of this cooperation in which the scope of the application of the EU posting of workers' directives in both countries was analysed.

There was a general double objective: on one hand, to explore the degree of knowledge of main social actors of labour involved in cross-border in Poland and Spain (public officers, trade unions members, posted workers, and employers); and on the other hand, to analyse their attitudes on working conditions of posting workers, in the framework of the EU Directive of posting of workers. Then, group discussions (in focus group format) were held with participants two times (in Poland and Spain) on issues related to employment, social issues, immigration, mobility and movement of workers.

Initially, 170 invitations (including 25 posted workers) were issued in each country. In total, 162 in Poland and 89 in Spain responded favourably. In addition, from the group discussions, it was agreed to also specifically collect information on working conditions in a survey with a brief questionnaire, because it is a relevant issue that requires specific attention. Therefore, convenience sampling (non-probability sampling technique) was used. This paper is based more specifically on results of the survey. Both the group discussions and the survey are developed following the guidelines of regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of April 27, 2016, regarding the protection of natural persons with regard to personal data processing and the free circulation of this data.

4.2. Data recollection and Sample

This paper summarises exclusively the final information on working conditions since the research used 2 steps to get information on posting of workers Directive and working conditions. In the first step, this research used the focus group technique which is the group discussion that uses communication between researchers and participants to obtain useful information on a topic of interest. The focus group is useful, and it is necessary when it comes to an open and unpredictable research topic. Regarding the development of the focus group with social actors of labour, the main topics centred the discussion were focused on issues such as the transposition of the Directives into the country's legislation, the public availability and access of information on posting workers, the actions of employers, the role of unions, the application of the directives in the country, the adaptation of the working conditions specified in the Directives and their application in reality, the use of the internal information market system, and the problems and difficulties of posted workers. In the second step, a simple questionnaire focused on the working conditions of posted workers was also developed, in which exploratory data was obtained in terms of frequencies and percentages. The questionnaire includes the aspects of the working conditions determined in the Directives which are presented in this study.

4.3. Instrument

To analyse the key aspects of the working conditions issued to the Directives on posting of workers (PWD 96/71/EC and PWD 67/2014/EU), a short questionnaire was designed for the survey. The questionnaire was conceived by experts in research in the

field of labour issues and posting of workers. It was composed of mixed items: on the one hand, the closed questions where the respondent could choose an option or a few options of answers; on the other hand, there were open questions that gave the possibility to participants to provide answers without limitations.

5. Results

The survey was focused on the achievement of the following objectives: (a) to explore the attitudes of the social actors of labour (civil servants, trade unions, employers, and employees) on the working conditions of the posted workers; (b) to study the irregularities and difficulties related to working conditions concerning the posting of workers. The main results of the survey are presented in frequencies and percentages comparing the two countries (Poland and Spain) of this study, with relevant participants' comments if appropriate.

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of participants. Most of them (54%) were male and 46% female. All participants were between 20 and 64 years old (mean age = 36 years, SD = 9.6). The sampling process of this study got responses from partners or groups of participants that belong to the following categories: public administration officers (65%), executives/members of association or trade union organisations (4%), posted workers (4%), members of NGO (14%), and employers (13%).

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of participants

	Poland		Spain		Total	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Sex	162		89		251	100
Men	93	37	42	17	135	54
Women	69	27	47	19	116	46
Age						
20 to 25 years	-	-	2	1	2	1
26 to 30 years	8	3	5	2	13	5
31 to 35 years	17	7	10	4	27	11
36 to 40 years	18	7	18	7	36	14
41 to 45 years	29	12	16	6	45	18
46 to 50 years	14	6	17	7	31	12
More than 50 years	76	30	21	8	97	39
Total	162	65	89	35	251	100
Participant's profile						
Public administration officer	126	50	38	15	164	65
Executive/member an association or trade union organisation	7	3	2	1	9	4
Posted worker	5	2	5	2	10	4
Member of NGO	6	2	30	12	36	14
Employer	18	7	14	6	32	13
Total	162	65	89	35	251	100

Regarding the knowledge of European directives (Directive 96/71/EC and Directive 2014/67/UE) on posted workers in the European Union, most participants (59%) considered that they had knowledge of the existence of European directive on posted workers as presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Awareness of existing of European directives (Directive 96/71/EC and Directive 2014/67/UE)

Are you aware of the existence of European Directives (Directive 96/71/EC and Directive 2014/67/UE) on posted workers in the European Union (EU)?	Poland		Spain		Total	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Yes	98	60	51	57	149	59
No	64	40	38	43	102	41
Total	162	100	89	100	251	100

The breakdown analysis shows that participants (respectively 60% in Poland and 59% in Spain) knew the existence of the European directives (Directive 96/71/EC and Directive 2014/67/UE) on posted workers in the European Union. On this issue, a sample of the participants' comments are as follows:

"I am aware of the existence of these European directives on posted workers but I have never had the opportunity to read them" (Participant 12, Poland).

"I usually have information about this type of regulations; and I read them sporadically; I think I should read more to have a good knowledge on posting Directives and how to use them" (participant 38, Spain).

I am not aware of the existence of such European Directives on posting workers" (participant 06, Poland).

"In my case, I know that posting of workers' regulations exist, but I have never got the occasion to use them" (participant 11, Spain).

The knowledge of the existence of European Directives is an imperative drive to devote adequate use of the EU regulations on this issue, to engage in genuine cooperation and to respect the rights of posting workers. Besides, Article 4(3) of the Directive sets out a clear obligation for Member States to take the appropriate measures to make the information in terms and conditions of employment generally available, not only to foreign service providers, but also to the posted workers concerned.

About 55% of the participants stated that there is social dumping in case of posting of workers in different countries (Table 3). Social dumping is a serious problem for posted workers according to participants from the two countries (55%). In Poland, 42% confirmed that there is a social dumping and only 13% in Spain. However, the number of people that argued that they were not completely sure about the social dumping was higher (36%); this was the case of Spain with 17%, and Poland with 19% of respondents. Some of the relevant comments of the participants:

"It is difficult to fight against social dumping, which is a scourge within the administrations; the case of posting workers is not an exception" (participant 14, Poland).

"Employers tend to favour local workers over posting workers. It is important to improve these aspects so that there is equality and social justice within the European Union" (participant, 20, Spain).

"The reinforcement of inter-state inspection within the European Union is the key to fighting social dumping. There are regulations that regulate the movement of workers

but there is still no common and adequate inspection system for monitoring workers; Furthermore, there is a lack of knowledge of the information system of the internal market of the European Union” (participant, 45, Poland).

Table 3. Existence of Social dumping in EU

There is social dumping (exploitation and offering of worse working conditions, below these which are acceptable).	Poland		Spain		Total	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Yes, there is social dumping	105	42	34	13	138	55
No, there is not social dumping	10	4	13	5	23	9
I am not completely sure about this issue	47	19	42	17	89	36
Total	162	65	89	35	251	100

As Table 4 illustrates, the results display relevant data to minimum salary levels, periods of work and minimum rest periods, and annual holidays. Only 22% of participants argued that the minimum salary levels are respected during the posting of workers (14% in Poland and 8% in Spain); meanwhile 35% disagreed (24% in Poland and 11% in Spain).

Table 4. Minimum conditions of work in EU Directives

	Poland		Spain		Total	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Minimum salary levels are respected.						
Totally agree	11	4	-	-	11	4
Agree	35	14	19	8	54	22
I do not know	48	19	34	14	82	33
Disagree	60	24	28	11	88	35
Totally disagree	8	3	8	3	16	6
Maximum periods of work and minimum rest periods are respected.						
Totally agree	8	3	-	-	8	3
Agree	45	18	18	7	63	25
I do not know	45	18	35	14	80	32
Disagree	58	23	30	12	88	35
Totally disagree	6	2	6	2	12	5
Minimum annual holidays are respected.						
Totally agree	13	5	-	-	13	5
Agree	55	22	16	6	71	28
I do not know	60	24	42	16	102	40
Disagree	30	12	25	10	55	22
Totally disagree	4	2	6	2	10	4
Total	162	65	89	35	251	100

It is also interesting to note that about 33% did not know if the minimum salary levels were respected or not. Participants clarify this issue as follows:

“It is the employer who determines the minimum wage to be paid to the displaced worker. When you come from a low-income country, you probably find the salary

offered attractive; which could even be lower than what local workers are paid” (participant, 62, Spain).

“We have no criteria to compare local worker conditions and those offered to displaced workers. There is a manifest lack of information on these matters” (participant 39, Poland).

To establish fair remuneration of posting workers, the objective should be to reduce the wage differences that could exist between posted and local workers. The employers apply the rules of the host country instead of the respect of the minimum rates of pay under the current Directive (PWD 96/71/EC and its Enforcement PWD 2014/67/UE). Consequently, employers have to offer the same working conditions and the same advantages, such as bonuses, allowances or pay increases according to seniority, to posted workers as to local ones. Regarding the maximum periods of work and minimum rest periods, 35% of them disagreed arguing that they are not respected (23% from Poland and 12% from Spain). Only 25% of them confirmed that they are respected (18% for Poland and 7% for Spain). The percentage of participants that declared that ‘they do not know’ reached 32% (18% in Poland and 14% in Spain).

In the context of Article 12 of Regulation No 883/2004 on the coordination of social security systems, PD A1 forms are used to certify that the holder is covered by the social security legislation of the Member State of origin. This form (PD A1) could also be issued for persons who are normally employed, self-employed or both employed and self-employed in two or more Member States (Art. 13 of Regulation (EC) No 883/2004 i). The gap in registered posted workers between PD A1 figures and national registers could be significant and lead consequently to fraud. Therefore, practical improvements should be done in the administrative requirements and control measures suggested by article 9(1).

The minimum annual holidays are the minimum period in which a worker is freed from his work obligations. On that issue, at least 40% of the participants stated that they did not know whether the minimum annual holidays are respected for posting workers (24% from Poland, and 16% from Spain). Only 28% claimed that they agreed (22% from Poland and 6% from Spain), meanwhile 22 did not. Within the scope of the Directive 2003/88, it must be calculated by reference to the days, hours and/or fractions of days or hours worked and specified in the contract of employment. The right to paid annual leave is granted to every worker even for every worker who is absent from work on sick leave, whether short or long term, regardless of whether he has in fact worked during the leave year. The Directive provides that paid annual leave is granted ‘in accordance with the conditions for entitlement to, and granting of, such leave laid down by national legislation and/or practice’. Moreover, the interpretative Communication on Directive 2003/88/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning certain aspects of the organisation of working time (2017/C 165/01) underlines that the annual leave entitlement is four weeks, meaning that workers must be freed from their work obligations for four calendar weeks, irrespective whether they work full-time or part-time.

As shown in table 5, the majority of participants (49%) are not clear about whether or not safety and hygiene conditions are respected in the case of posted workers. In Spain, 27% consider that these conditions are guaranteed, compared to only 20% in Poland. There is a lack of knowledge about the conditions under which displaced workers work, at least in the case of the participants in this study. Two comments on this topic summarise the situation as follows:

“It is difficult to obtain information about displaced workers, much less about their working conditions; Both employers and workers themselves do not provide this type of data” (participant 123, Poland).

“In the workplace, working conditions are the same for all, both for local and displaced workers. In a given position, if the conditions are good, they will be for everyone; and if they are bad they will affect everyone equally” (Participant 57, Spain).

Table 5. Conditions of occupational safety and hygiene

In general, the conditions of occupational safety and hygiene at work for posted workers are guaranteed.	Poland		Spain		Total	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Totally agree	7	3	5	2	12	5
Agree	42	17	14	6	56	22
I do not know/ no answer	78	31	46	18	124	49
Disagree	30	12	20	8	50	20
Totally disagree	5	2	4	2	9	4
Total	162	65	89	35	251	100

Safety and hygiene conditions at work are an important and delicate issue for workers. In the case of displaced workers, they can be one of the sources of exploitation. It is possible that some companies develop abusive practices that lead to the deterioration of the working conditions of displaced workers. This could be critical if the employer does not offer good protection of working conditions related to the physical environment, stress and noise levels, the degree of safety or danger and risks of accidents, etc..

6. Discussion and conclusions

The main objective of this exploratory study was to analyse the attitudes of main social actors of labour involved in cross-border in Poland and Spain (public officers, trade unions members, posted workers, and employers) on working conditions of posting workers, in the framework of the EU Directive of posting of workers. People aspire to have not just a job, but a good occupation with suitable working conditions. In their ordinary workplace or in the posting of workers' scenario, employees aspire to have adequate working conditions. Posting of Workers Directive (PWD) plays a pivotal role in the EU internal market to ensure the posted workers 'rights and to prevent unfair competition for cross border provision of services. Working conditions remain a relevant issue that is still raising problems of unfair practices, social dumping and abuses. Since 1996, the European Union has established the Directive (PWD 96/71/EC) to ensure that the rights of posting workers are respected in any of the State members. However, some cases of violation of workers 'rights required the reinforcement of the Directive by enacting the PWD 2014/67/EU and the Directive (PWD 2018/957) which has been transposed to national laws. The objective of this exploratory study was to study the attitudes of social actors involved in mobility and posting of the workers' activities (public officers, trade unions members, posted workers, posting workers and employers) from Poland and Spain on the working conditions in the framework of the EU Directive of posting of workers.

Like the rest of the EU countries, Spain and Poland have transposed the Directives into their national legislation to ensure the respect of the posted workers' rights. The results of this research showed that participants considered that the working conditions are respected with limitations in terms defined by EU Directives (PWD 96/71/EC and Directive 2014/67/EU). Most participants from Poland and Spain alleged that they were aware of the existence of European directives (Directive 96/71/EC and Enforcement Directive 2014/67/UE) on posted workers in the European Union. They underlined the existence of social dumping in some cases of posting of workers. They considered that the posting of workers' activities could expose the employee to the risk of being subject of undeclared work practices. The fair application of the posting of workers Directives is important to avoid abuses and violations of the rights of workers.

One of the key aspects of the working conditions is the remuneration. Participants in this study underlined that the minimum wage is not respected. One of the problems is the interpretation of the EU Directives which is not clear at all in many aspects, particularly on the equity between local and posted workers on the wage issues. The EU Directives (PWD 96/71/EC and Directive 2014/67/EU) establish a structural differentiation of wage rules applying to posted and local workers; this is a source of the institutional source of segmentation in the labour market. There are three causes of remuneration differentiation set in place by the Directive: (a) the Directive determines the minimum rates of pay only, as part of a "hard core of clearly defined protective rules" in the hosting Member State; this situation is unclear for employers, and source of wage discrimination. Obviously, the minimum pay is defined either by the law or by universally applicable collective agreements which have been declared universally applicable. In the absence of universally applicable collective agreements, it is difficult to determine the minimum and maximum pay. Therefore, Directive should propose mechanisms of structural wage of minimum and maximum pay between posted and local workers to avoid the gap that leads to social dumping and discrimination; (b) The definition of 'minimum rates of pay' in the Directive is unclear because it may differ from one country to another. If 'minimum rates of pay' also includes certain bonuses or allowances as part of pay, they can be constituent parts of the pay in some Member States, but they are not in others. The lack of a clear definition and standard applicable generates uncertainty and could lead to salary discrimination and social dumping.

The Directive (PWD 2018/957) entered into force in 2020, and its evaluation is expected during the coming years. This revised Directive is expected to improve the practices of structural wage in local and hosting countries for "equal work, equal salary" in the EU. By the time, the juridical cases analysed by the European Court of Justice could continue contributing to the clarification of the definition of "same pay for the same work in the same place", as well as working conditions. To establish fair remuneration of posting workers according to Directive (PWD 2018/957), the objective should be to reduce the wage differences that exist between posted and local workers. The employers should apply the rules of transparent remuneration instead of applying the rules of respect of the minimum rates of pay under the previous Directive. Thus, employers have to offer the same working conditions and same advantages, such as bonuses, allowances or pay increases according to seniority, to posted workers as to local ones.

To protect workers' health and safety, the EU determines the minimum standards working hours applicable in member States. In some cases, the Court of Justice considers the criteria of the 'the worker is working' related to the need for the worker to be 'at the

workplace' or 'at a place determined by his employer. The EU Directives (PWD 96/71/EC and PWD 2014/67/EU) are useful instruments that are trying to improve the rights of the posting workers by increasing the awareness of workers and companies about their rights and obligations as regards the terms and conditions of employment. They manage to improve the cooperation between national authorities in charge of posting and reinforce some key aspects related to (a) maximum periods of work minimum resting periods, paid holidays and rates of payments, including any overtime; (b) hiring conditions; (c) health, safety and hygiene; (d) regulations within work environments; (e) protective regulations with regards to the employment of pregnant women or women who have recently delivered a child; (f) non-discriminatory and equal treatment regulations. The EU has made considerable efforts to improve the working conditions of the posting workers by promulgating the posting of workers Directives. It is expected to reduce some cases of abuse and violations reported in some countries. It is important to increase the availability and dissemination of information on the posting of workers in the EU countries so that the information can be available for all social actors of labour (employees, employers, unions, civil society, government). There is still a certain lack of knowledge and information about all the conditions related to posted workers; this remains an important challenge for EU Member State countries. The working conditions in case of posting workers is a challenge that the EU is trying to improve urgently since the posting of workers is one of the important issues for the social dialogue and social cohesion between European countries.

Besides, it is important to underline that organisational changes, new design of working environment, new positions, modalities of work (in-person work, teleworking and hybrid work) are introducing changes in working conditions which have an impact on employees. In the case of posting of workers, the European Union should encourage companies to continue to improve the working conditions in each form of work. The EU Directives need improvement to adapt the normative to the main changes which are caused by globalisation, and digital transformation.

The recent Directive (PWD 2018/957) is expected to improve some weaknesses detected in PWD 96/71/EC and PWD 2014/67/EU, particularly related to working conditions. Despite its adoption in 2020, the PWD 2018/957 presents some weaknesses that are still unsolved (e.g. joint inspectorate, cooperation between countries, availability of information on posting of workers' activities). EU Members will require to work and cooperate jointly to take to solve persistent problems of cross-borders and internal market integration. Besides, European Union needs to improve its system of inquiries and exchange of information between the competent authorities of each EU country to reinforce the cross-border inspection. The transnational inspection needs more efficient system of information exchange, means for alerting on unfair situations to prevent and to combat irregular practices (frauds, avoidance of taxes pays, lowering the social security costs, social dumping, etc.). In that context, the role of the European Labour Authority (ELA) should be reinforced; it is the institution that plays the role of European Union umbrella in terms of transparent and comprehensive transnational approach in the labour mobility and provision of cross-border posting of workers. ELA is expected to assume the role of labour inspectorate at the EU level because the joint inspection experiences have not worked as predicted. Till now the joint inspection between countries faces problems of coordination, lack of analogue institution or agency in the other country.

Another problem detected in this exploratory study is lack of information among people that are working as social actors of labour on posting of workers and mobility. It is

important to have sound information on posting activities to contribute significantly in their daily activities and to act as liaisons and experts. More research is needed to determine the impact of availability of information on efficiency of actors involved in posting activities and labour mobility. Furthermore, it will be interesting to analyse the attitudes of each group of the social actors involved in this preliminary study to get more data on working conditions and to determine the level of knowledge and implications with posting of workers' activities. In this article, researchers, political leaders, and managers will find a relevant conceptual framework on working conditions in the context of workers' mobility. Besides, it brings an interesting perspective on the posting of workers' directive as an instrument of social cohesion and integration within the EU.

Declaration of interest statement

The author declares no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Data access statement

The datasets used during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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